

Balancing Efficacy and Risks: High-Dose Antibiotic Strategies in the Management of Sepsis in Intensive Care Units in Ecuador Balancing Efficacy and Risks

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ABSTRACT

Antibiotic resistance is a pressing global health challenge, particularly in critical care settings. In Ecuador, intensive care units frequently employ high-dose antibiotic regimens for sepsis management, despite limited evidence validating this practice. This perspective evaluates current literature, highlighting the benefits and risks of high-dose strategies and their potential contribution to antimicrobial resistance (AMR). The article underscores the urgent need for research on dose-response relationships, resistance mechanisms, and optimized dosing strategies to balance efficacy and safety in sepsis treatment within resource-limited healthcare systems.

Keywords: Antimicrobial Resistance; High-Dose Antibiotics; Sepsis management; Critical care; Antibiotic stewardship

INTRODUCTION

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a mounting global health challenge, complicating the treatment of infections, increasing healthcare costs, and contributing to significant morbidity and mortality. Data from 2019 highlight AMR’s devastating public health impact, with bacterial resistance directly causing 1.27 million deaths worldwide and contributing to an additional 4.95 million fatalities.^[1] The rise in antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains has been particularly pronounced in hospital settings, where extensive antibiotic use, especially in intensive care units (ICUs), creates a fertile environment for the development and spread of resistant infections.^[2-4]

One of the most concerning environments for AMR proliferation is hospital intensive care units (ICUs), where antibiotic usage is pervasive. Critically ill patients, particularly those experiencing sepsis or septic shock, necessitate rapid and aggressive antibiotic interventions to mitigate treatment failures and reduce mortality.^[5-11] In Ecuador, it is standard clinical practice in ICUs to employ elevated or double-dose antibiotics as an initial or loading strategy in patients with septic shock. This approach seeks to quickly achieve therapeutic drug concentrations, especially in the critical first 24 hours, by administering doses exceeding standard recommendations, such as 2 g of meropenem every 8 hours without immediate renal adjustment. However, there is a concerning lack of international evidence validating the safety and efficacy of this practice. Furthermore, its potential impact on AMR is largely unexplored, highlighting the need for a critical analysis of this approach.

DISCUSSION

The pathophysiology of sepsis often requires aggressive fluid resuscitation, which increases the volume of distribution (Vd) of hydrophilic antibiotics, necessitating higher doses to achieve therapeutic levels.^[6-8] Despite this physiological rationale, there is no definitive consensus on whether high-dose antibiotic regimens prevent mortality or contribute to AMR.

Several studies provide insights into the effects of high-dose strategies:

- Yadav et al.^[12] demonstrated reduced treatment failure rates with high-dose cephalexin in cellulitis patients, though adverse effects such as nausea and diarrhea were more common.
- Tichy et al.^[13] observed improved clinical outcomes and cost-effectiveness with high-dose meropenem in pneumonia cases but did not evaluate its direct impact on AMR.
- Martin-Loeches et al.^[14] and Timsit et al.^[15] highlighted limitations in standard dosing for high-risk populations, but neither addressed high-dose regimens comprehensively.

While these findings suggest that high-dose antibiotics can enhance immediate clinical outcomes, they also underscore the trade-offs between efficacy, safety, and the potential for resistance.

The Ecuadorian Perspective: ICU Practices and Challenges

In Ecuador, intensive care specialists frequently administer high or double-dose antibiotic regimens during the initial phase of septic shock management. This practice aligns with the urgent need to reduce mortality in critically ill patients but raises concerns about toxicity, resource utilization, and AMR risks. Additionally, healthcare systems in low- and middle-income countries, including Ecuador, face unique challenges that exacerbate AMR:

- Widespread misuse of antibiotics in clinical and agricultural settings.
- Limited availability of rapid diagnostic tools, leading to empiric therapy.
- Poor infection control and hygiene practices in hospitals.^[16]

In these settings, double-dosing antibiotics without robust evidence may further accelerate AMR, complicating infection control efforts and limiting future therapeutic options.

Weighing Immediate Benefits Against Long-Term Risks

Double or high-dose antibiotic regimens aim to rapidly achieve therapeutic drug concentrations, particularly in sepsis, where delayed therapy is associated with increased mortality.^[6,17] The common practice of administering

double doses within the first 24 hours is often driven by the critical nature of sepsis. However, such strategies may inadvertently promote the selection of resistant bacterial strains.^[3,18]

The **mutant prevention concentration (MPC)** concept offers a theoretical framework to mitigate resistance risks, suggesting that maintaining drug concentrations above the MPC may prevent the emergence of resistant mutants.^[23] However, the practical application of MPC-based dosing in clinical settings is limited by concerns about toxicity and logistical challenges.

Existing studies provide limited and often inconclusive evidence regarding the relationship between high-dose antibiotic regimens and AMR. For instance:

- Van Duijn et al.^[19] found no significant difference in resistance acquisition between antibiotic cycling and mixing strategies, indicating the complexity of resistance dynamics in ICU settings.
- Cižman and Plankar^[20] proposed that larger doses administered over shorter periods may reduce resistance risks, though this hypothesis requires further validation.

The critical gap in the literature underscores the urgent need for research tailored to ICU practices in resource-constrained settings, such as those in Ecuador, where high-dose antibiotics are frequently used.

Implications for Future Research:

Given the lack of definitive evidence linking high-dose antibiotic regimens to AMR, future research should prioritize:

1. **Dose-Response Studies:** To explore how increasing antibiotic doses influence resistance development, particularly in ICUs where sepsis management demands aggressive therapy.
2. **Longitudinal Studies:** To track resistance patterns in patients receiving high-dose regimens over time, providing real-world insights into the impact of these practices.
3. **Genetic and Molecular Analysis:** To identify biomarkers for early detection of resistance linked to high-dose antibiotics.
4. **Optimization of Antibiotic Stewardship:** Evaluating how high-dose strategies interact with antibiotic cycling or de-escalation protocols to minimize resistance risks.

CONCLUSION

High-dose antibiotic regimens are a cornerstone of sepsis management in ICUs, particularly in Ecuador, where clinical practices often diverge from global guidelines. While these strategies address the immediate need for effective therapy in critically ill patients, their long-term implications for AMR remain poorly understood. Addressing this knowledge gap through targeted research is essential for optimizing treatment protocols that balance efficacy and safety, ensuring sustainable antibiotic use in critical care settings.

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Ethics statement. The authors declare that the present study was conducted under the strictest ethical conditions. The research was approved by Nevşehir Hacı Bektaş Veli University Non-invasive Clinical Research Publication Ethics Committee (Decision number: 2023/12, Date: 19.04.2023)

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Availability of data and materials

The datasets are available from the corresponding author upon request

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. Antimicrobial resistance. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/es/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/antimicrobial-resistance> [Accessed 14th August 2024].
2. Huemer M, Mairpady Shambat S, Brugger SD, Zinkernagel AS. Antibiotic resistance and persistence—Implications for human health and treatment perspectives. EMBO reports. 2020;21(12):e51034.
3. Salam MdA, Al-Amin MdY, Salam MT, Pawar JS, Akhter N, Rabaan AA, et al. Antimicrobial Resistance: A Growing Serious Threat for Global Public Health. Healthcare. 2023;11(13):1946.
4. Mississippi State Department of Health. About Antibiotic Resistance. Mississippi State Department of Health.
5. Póvoa P, Moniz P, Pereira JG, Coelho L. Optimizing Antimicrobial Drug Dosing in Critically Ill Patients. Microorganisms. 2021;9(7):1401.
6. Martínez ML, Plata-Menchaca EP, Ruiz-Rodríguez JC, Ferrer R. An approach to antibiotic treatment in patients with sepsis. Journal of Thoracic Disease. 2020;12(3):1007–1021.
7. Vélez JW, Aragon DC, Donadi EA, Carloti APCP. Risk factors for mortality from sepsis in an intensive care unit in Ecuador: A prospective study. Medicine. 2022;101(11).
8. Bruhn CA, Pairumani MR, Hernández PG. Management of the patient in septic shock. Revista Médica Clínica Las Condes. 2011;22(3):293–301.
9. Chinemerem Nwobodo D, Ugwu MC, Oliseloke Anie C, Al-Ouqaili MTS, Chinedu Ikem J, Victor Chigozie U, et al. Antibiotic resistance: The challenges and some emerging strategies for tackling a global menace. Journal of Clinical Laboratory Analysis. 2022;36(9): e24655.
10. Uddin TM, Chakraborty AJ, Khusro A, Zidan BRM, Mitra S, Emran TB, et al. Antibiotic resistance in microbes: History, mechanisms, therapeutic strategies and future prospects. Journal of Infection and Public Health. 2021;14(12):1750–1766.
11. Cotta MO, Roberts JA, Lipman J. Antibiotic dose optimization in critically ill patients. Medicina Intensiva (English Edition). 2015;39(9): 563–572.

12. Yadav K, Eagles D, Perry JJ, Taljaard M, Sandino-Gold G, Nemnom MJ, et al. High-dose cephalexin for cellulitis: a pilot randomized controlled trial. Canadian Journal of Emergency Medicine. 2023;25(1):22–30.
13. Tichy E, Torres A, Bassetti M, Kongnakorn T, Di Virgilio R, Irani P, et al. Cost-effectiveness Comparison of Ceftazidime/Avibactam Versus Meropenem in the Empirical Treatment of Hospital-acquired Pneumonia, Including Ventilator-associated Pneumonia, in Italy. Clinical Therapeutics. 2020;42(5): 802–817.
14. Martin-Loeches I, Timsit JF, Kollef MH, Wunderink RG, Shime N, Nováček M, et al. Clinical and microbiological outcomes, by causative pathogen, in the ASPECT-NP randomized, controlled, Phase 3 trial comparing ceftolozane/tazobactam and meropenem for treatment of hospital-acquired/ventilator-associated bacterial pneumonia. Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy. 2022;77(4): 1166–1177.
15. Timsit JF, Huntington JA, Wunderink RG, Shime N, Kollef MH, Kivistik Ü, et al. Ceftolozane/tazobactam versus meropenem in patients with ventilated hospital-acquired bacterial pneumonia: subset analysis of the ASPECT-NP randomized, controlled phase 3 trial. Critical Care. 2021;25(1):290.
16. Bokhary H, Pangesti KNA, Rashid H, Abd El Ghany M, Hill-Cawthorne GA. Travel-Related Antimicrobial Resistance: A Systematic Review. Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease. 2021;6(1): 11.
17. Pasquau-Liaño J. Timing in antibiotic therapy: when and how to start, de-escalate and stop antibiotic therapy. Proposals from a stablished antimicrobial stewardship program. Revista Española de Quimioterapia. 2022;35(Suppl3):102–107.
18. Ahmed SK, Hussein S, Qurbani K, Ibrahim RH, Fareeq A, Mahmood KA, et al. Antimicrobial resistance: Impacts, challenges, and future prospects. Journal of Medicine, Surgery, and Public Health. 2024;2:100081.
19. Van Duijn PJ, Verbrugghe W, Jorens PG, Spöhr F, Schedler D, Deja M, et al. The effects of antibiotic cycling and mixing on acquisition of antibiotic resistant bacteria in the ICU: A post-hoc individual patient analysis of a prospective cluster-randomized crossover study. Yahav D (ed.) PLOS ONE. 2022;17(5):e0265720.
20. Cižman M, Plankar Srovin T. Antibiotic consumption and resistance of gram-negative pathogens (collateral damage). GMS Infectious Diseases; 2018 Aug 9:6:Doc05.